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CONTENTS

The role and prospects of innovations in uzbekistan’s strategy for transition to a green economy	4
Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna	
Evaluation of the vape category among e-cigarette smokers in Uzbekistan.....	9
S.M. Mirzaliev, G.K. Abdurakhmanova, M.O. Kurolov, Judy Smetana, Krissy Lewis	
Features of the south korean education system and possibilities of their application in Uzbekistan	23
Mukhamadjanov Shakhriyor Solijon ugli	
Exploring the directions of sustainable development of tourism in uzbekistan.....	28
Khusniddin Egamnazarov	
Influence of the number of workers on the profitability of enterprises.....	35
Gafurova Azizaxon Fatixovna	
Strategies for differentiating teaching instructions in the esp classroom	39
Shahnoza Berdiyeva Xolmaxmatovna	
Factors affecting remote services of banking	43
Khudoyorov O.O.	
Digital transformation of manufacturing	48
Kudaynazarova Dilnaz Koshkarbaevna	
Forming important methods for nurturing students’ educational initiatives based on national-cultural approaches	54
Azimova Nilufar Nuriddinovna	
The multifaceted dimensions of poverty in Asia: a comprehensive analysis.....	61
Amirdjanova Sitara Sunnat kizi	
Spiral models of innovative development: triple, quadruple and five helix models.....	66
Sultanova Munisa Samat kizi	
Strategic development of mice tourism in Spain: trends and implications.....	72
Bahromov Behzod, Egamnazarov Husniddin	
Development of food market infrastructure	77
Daminova Ugiloy Mirzakul kizi	
The mechanisms for developing students’ motivation for independent learning through educational project technology	83
Kasimova (Mulladjanova) Nasiba Azimdjanovna	
Program-based budgeting and its application potential in Uzbekistan.....	89
Ganieva Malika Maksudovna	
Management of integrated manufacturing enterprises	92
Tursunova Zarnigor Rustamovna	
Building a sustainable workforce: the role of green hrm in driving corporate environmental responsibility.....	96
Omanova Nargiza Rustam kizi	
The main features of e-commerce dynamics in world countries.....	105
Dilafruz Sodikova	
Theoretical foundations and macroeconomic impact of foreign direct investment: insights and implications for developing economies	113
Ibragimov Ganijon Gayratovich	

DEVELOPMENT OF FOOD MARKET INFRASTRUCTURE

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Abstract: This article is devoted to revealing the meaning of the concept of food market infrastructure. Market infrastructure includes various economic institutions and services that contribute to the effective functioning of the economic system. The article analyzes the main elements of food market infrastructure, including financial markets, commodity exchanges, credit and insurance issues, as well as the importance of transport and communication systems. The article serves to expand the understanding of the sustainable development of market infrastructure and its role in the economic system from a theoretical point of view.

Key words: infrastructure, food market infrastructure, food market infrastructure functions, food market infrastructure elements.

INTRODUCTION

The mechanism of the food market is explained by the interaction of objective factors, phenomena and processes in the process of production, distribution, exchange and consumption of food products. The effective functioning of this market is associated with the needs of the population, domestic production capabilities and the development of interregional relations. The efficiency of the food market in our country, in turn, directly affects the level of development of the infrastructure serving it. The relevance of this topic is determined by the need to improve the main processes aimed at meeting the needs of the food market.

In addition, the effectiveness of communication between producers and consumers is also important for the success of the food market. It is necessary to introduce innovative approaches and modern technologies to improve the quality of food products, stabilize prices and satisfy consumers. At the same time, state policy and economic strategies also play an important role in the development of the food market, as they help regulate production and distribution systems. The development of the food market contributes not only to economic stability, but also to increasing the well-being of the population.

Of course, the formation and development of the food market is primarily associated with the volume of goods and services that play an important role in the development of territorial relations. In this process, in turn, the presence of developed agricultural production and the food industry is also important. Another important condition for ensuring the positive and balanced development of the food market is the presence of sufficient infrastructure to serve the market.

In other words, the presence of the necessary mass of goods and solvent demand to ensure effective communication between producers and consumers is not enough. It is also very important to have a set of networks that support and facilitate these processes. Within these networks, elements such as transport, storage, distribution and marketing services find their place.

At the same time, state policy and economic strategies also play an important role in the successful functioning of the food market. They help stabilize the market by regulating production and distribution systems. In such conditions, consumers will have more convenient opportunities to satisfy their needs, and producers will have the opportunity to effectively present their products. The development of the food market will not only ensure economic stability, but also serve to increase the well-being of the population.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

In the economic literature, the concept of “infrastructure” is interpreted differently by domestic economists and foreign researchers. The term infrastructure was first used in economic analysis at the beginning of the 20th century to designate objects and structures that ensure the normal functioning of the armed forces. This term comes from the Latin words “infra” - under, and “structure” - structure, location, i.e. in other words, the concept of infrastructure can be interpreted as a “foundation” or “substructure” [1].

According to market theories, “infrastructure” is a set of market institutions that ensure the interconnection of the main macroeconomic flows. At the same time, there is an interpretation of this concept in a broad sense as a system of institutions of all local markets, while in a narrow sense, material objects are included in the concept of infrastructure. To fully understand the essence of the concept of infrastructure, it is necessary to turn to the views of researchers of this term, who, along with their subjective points of view, can also identify objective aspects of understanding this concept.

The founder of the theory of infrastructure was R. Lohimsen, who classified infrastructure as a set of material, institutional and individual equipment at the disposal of economic entities, which allows for full integration and a high level of economic activity in the purposeful distribution of resources. Thus, infrastructure was the material and technical side of production relations.

In a more detailed definition of the essence of infrastructure, according to J. Stein, P. Rosenstein-Rodan, A. Pisenti, I. K. Belyaevsky, A. Y. Sharipov, G. Muftiev and other researchers, the concept of infrastructure is inextricably linked with production and economic relations, where infrastructure is a set of material means of labor (material and technical structures, equipment or means of communication). This approach, in our opinion, determines the content, role and tasks of this concept from the point of view of the material form of its origin. At the same time, it is necessary to take into account the nature of infrastructure in the system of categories that predetermine production and economic relations. Thus, the consideration of the nature of infrastructure depends on the specific characteristics of various spheres of social production, which are historically inseparable from the development of the social division of labor [2].

B. P. Fedko, N. G. Fedko noted that modern market infrastructure is its integral and integral part, determining the effectiveness of the activities of all elements of the market. Due to the presence of various components of the infrastructure, the market is a cultural form of relations between people. It is especially important that the elements of the infrastructure are not imposed on business structures from the outside, but are a product of economic relations. At the same time, the authors of this study understand market infrastructure as a set of activities that ensure the effective functioning of market economy objects and their unity in a given real market space.

Generalizing the above definitions of infrastructure as an economic category allows us to conclude that researchers characterize the substantive part of the concept or determine the scope of activity of the category under study [3].

The problem of infrastructure formation has brought together many complex regional problems, the solution of which to a certain extent depends on the further improvement of the economic system.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study used the comparative analysis method to identify the general and specific aspects of the food market infrastructure. Using the abstraction method, various views on the term infrastructure were summarized, which allows us to study a certain group of phenomena related to the food market infrastructure and understand its true meaning. Through the logical methods used in the research process, a theoretical generalization of the food market infrastructure was developed and its significance was clearly substantiated.

In addition, the study also deeply studied the interconnections between various components of the food market infrastructure, such as transport, storage, distribution and marketing systems. Each of these components is important for the effective functioning of the market, and their interaction ensures the stability of the food supply. Also, during the study, the food market infrastructure was considered not only from an economic, but also from a social and environmental perspective. This, in turn, ensured the comprehensiveness of the research results and the integrated approach necessary for food market development. As a result, the study generated new knowledge on the development of food market infrastructure and laid the foundation for future research in this area.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Market infrastructure, which is a set of objects and institutional structures that ensure the implementation of material, financial and informational relations between food market entities, is integrated into a single chain

of production, circulation and consumption sectors, thereby ensuring the continuity of the reproduction process.

An analysis of the relationship between the existing capabilities of market infrastructure and the level of food production showed that most regions of Uzbekistan are characterized by underdevelopment of warehousing, specialized transport, tarpaulin and container stock, trading floors of food stores, economic and information infrastructure.

Of course, infrastructure objects themselves do not directly contribute to GDP, but they help to accelerate commodity turnover and, therefore, capital turnover, and, as a result, indirectly affect the growth of GDP. Therefore, in order to create normal economic conditions in the food market and in the region as a whole, state and regional authorities should begin to develop market infrastructure.

In addition, the annual growth in the number of retail outlets in our country indicates their insufficient capacity to ensure the normal satisfaction of the needs of the population. It should be noted that the growth of retail space is mainly observed in non-food products, and thus does not solve the problems of infrastructural development of the food market.

Thus, one of the directions for the development of the infrastructure of the food market should be the optimization of the structure of trade enterprises, which includes increasing the number and share of large food stores, which allows for the mechanization of trade and warehouse operations, modernization of trading equipment, refrigeration equipment and cashier services. The analysis showed that today there are 3,402 refrigerated warehouses in our country. Also, during the years of the study, fruit and vegetable processing centers with a capacity of 67 thousand tons, sorting and packaging centers with a capacity of 7 thousand tons, refrigeration centers with a capacity of 60 thousand tons and agrologistics centers with a capacity of 190 thousand tons were launched.¹ In turn, the implementation of this direction requires improving the technical policy in the development of food market infrastructure.

Practice shows that the basis of economic development is innovation. It should be noted that due to innovation, the needs of the population are increasing and changing, and their full creation largely depends not only on the emergence of qualitatively new goods, but also on new methods of their implementation, new methods of stimulating demand, etc. Without relevant innovations, the effectiveness of the development of the market infrastructure of the food market is also impossible.

Another important area of development of the food market infrastructure should be the improvement of the information infrastructure, which includes marketing centers, advertising agencies, permanent wholesale fairs and exhibitions, IT and communication tools. Today, business entities operating in the food market, most of which are medium and small enterprises, do not have the opportunity to independently conduct full market research. The lack of necessary and reliable information on the market situation does not allow entities to make decisions that will increase their competitiveness. To change the current situation, it is necessary to improve the information infrastructure of the food market, and primarily its statistical component.

The transformation of the statistical system requires the introduction of new methods of statistical verification, improvement of the management of the statistical system, training of personnel and re-equipment of computing equipment, effective storage, exchange and dissemination of data for the benefit of users.

The main directions of improving the statistical information system in the field of data collection should be as follows:

- modernization of existing software for entering paper forms of statistical reports;
- introduction of methods and tools for collecting data in electronic form directly from enterprises;
- use of automated data entry tools by scanning;
- development of specialized data entry tools for monitoring the food market.

Improving the information exchange and distribution system also includes a number of measures: modernization of the technology for using data exchange arrays; improvement of industrial exchange tools, etc. Considering that the development of the food market largely depends on interregional relations, it is advisable to create appropriate regional statistical bodies in the relevant regions that would collect, process and present information on the state and development trends of the relevant market. At the same time, it is necessary to maintain district statistics of its development, not forgetting that the food market has its own characteristics within the region in each individual urban area.

Unfortunately, at the present stage, the indicators provided by official statistics do not allow for a complete and adequate analysis of the state and development trends of the food market. Therefore, the set of indicators used in food market statistics requires significant updating. For a complete analysis of the regional food market, it is advisable to include in the indicators data on changes in market opportunities for individual product groups, as well as changes in the market share occupied by various firms. The demographic component also needs updating. Improving the information provision of the food market is associated with the introduction of new

¹ <https://stat.uz/uz/>

scientifically based methods for predicting consumer demand for solvency, studying its dynamics and spatial and temporal characteristics.

Of course, the effective development of the food market is impossible without an appropriate structure of investment and credit organizations, taking into account the specifics of the activities of these market entities.

For the development of the food market, the development of infrastructure facilities that will help promote goods and stimulate demand is of particular importance. One of the directions in this regard should be the introduction of marketing tools not only by individual business entities, but also at the level of regional authorities.

The effective implementation of comprehensive programs for the development of regions largely depends on the rational creation and improvement of a network of infrastructure facilities that directly affect the current level of economic activity in their territory and the prospects for the development of the productive forces of each region. The development of proposals for its development in different regions, which differ in their specific natural conditions and socio-economic structure, will be even more important.

Regional infrastructure is a complex, integrated, multifunctional system of economic entities and factors designed to ensure the civilized nature of the activities of market entities of the region. Infrastructure is designed to provide external non-production services necessary for the effective functioning of economic entities of the region and the economy as a whole. At the same time, the main object that determines the functional purpose and essential features of the infrastructure is the sphere of movement of goods and services. Ensuring the conditions for the transformation of goods and services into consumers should be determined by the appropriate infrastructure of various types of markets. It should be noted that infrastructure objects work directly for the needs of a particular territory, primarily related to the needs of business and the population, as well as the main factors determining the commodity specialization and conjuncture of a particular market (formation of supply and demand, price ratio, composition of market participants, etc.) [4].

The general functional purpose of the infrastructure is to provide socially useful non-production services of a commercial, information, logistical, marketing nature, as well as services for the storage, transportation and packaging of products. This can be fully linked to the food market infrastructure, which is designed to ensure the continuity of the process of reproduction in the sale of goods and services. In fact, the entire food system is based on the food market infrastructure.

Thus, the specific features of the sphere of circulation of goods and services determine the specific features of the infrastructure, the laws of its formation and development. According to the analysis of theoretical concepts, the essence of the infrastructure of the food market is determined by its main functions in the process of circulation of goods and services in the regional market. (Figure 1)

Figure 1. Main functions of food market infrastructure²

² Developed by the author

At the same time, the implementation of the presented infrastructure functions determines the conditions for the formation and emergence of the main components of the food market infrastructure. It is also possible to identify two forms of manifestation of market infrastructure. First, the circulation of goods and services between producers and consumers leads to the emergence of objects and infrastructure factors of a particular market. Secondly, the formation of market infrastructure precedes the process of circulation of goods and services in the market. Thus, the functions performed by the food market infrastructure can be associated with the nature of the formation of its main components, and on this basis, a model of the effective functioning of the food market infrastructure can be developed.

Thus, according to the structural composition, the food market infrastructure defines a set of interrelated and interacting elements, the system of which forms the infrastructure complex of the food market.

The functioning of the market infrastructure complex is based on the following aspects:

considering the infrastructure complex of the food market as a single integrated system, which implies its formation on the basis of all structural elements;

improving the interdependence and interdependence of all components of the system;

continuous improvement of the facilities themselves, which are included in the infrastructure complex of the consumer market.

Taking into account the above aspects, the main elements of the infrastructure complex are identified and grouped into several systems as follows (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Main elements and systems of the food market infrastructure complex³

The elements of the food market infrastructure complex presented in this way make it possible to determine its role and significance in the system of the food market.

The implementation of economic relations between market counterparties in the economy objectively requires a mechanism that controls any means, a whole set of measures. In the field of commodity circulation, such a mechanism is mediation on the basis of economic relations in their various organizational and economic forms. These relations determine the actual movement of products in the market, the provision of various services. Therefore, it is necessary to develop a mechanism for the functioning of the infrastructure complex of the region, taking into account the specific features and characteristics of the market. The mechanism for the development of market infrastructure is based on the development of a model of the effective functioning of the structural elements of the food market infrastructure complex.

The development and implementation of a model of the infrastructure components of the complex is one of the means of economic diagnostics of the market infrastructure of the region, the main tasks of which are currently to create an economic environment for the formation and development of a system of local markets, the necessary economic conditions for the development of economic entities, ensuring material, financial,

³ Developed by the author

labor and informational ties between economic entities at all levels. serves to improve the quality of life of the population.

Thus, within the framework of this study, it is appropriate to consider the problems of the functioning and development of the regional infrastructure taking into account economic specialization, national and historical traditions of production and consumption of products in the territory of the subject of the Russian Federation.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The study of the interaction of the elements of the food and services market infrastructure allows, firstly, to determine the range of entities and factors participating in the process of commodity exchange, and secondly, to identify the main criteria for regulating market development. For example, the characteristics of consumer market objects, in particular food and non-food stores, supermarkets, hypermarkets and agricultural markets, catering establishments, household service establishments, for example, the pedestrian accessibility of the consumer market object, the volume of retail space per capita, etc. Thirdly, the developed model of the functioning of the market infrastructure determines the connection of the elements with the aspects of the cause-and-effect relationship of their origin and development, based on the systematic nature of all its elements.

An efficiently functioning economy can only be created with the help of an effective infrastructure that ensures complex and long-term cooperation between market participants. Creating a competitive market environment and activating entrepreneurial activity depend on the effective functioning and development of infrastructure.

Infrastructure is part of the market, therefore it is objectively necessary for the formation, sustainable development and functioning of market mechanisms, optimization of the functioning of various market laws, ensuring the movement of goods, and meeting the needs of society. One of the features of the current stage of the formation of the country's modern market system is the aggravation of the problem of increasing the role of infrastructure and its further development and improvement.

The main reason for the formation and separation of the food market infrastructure as an independent economic sector was the social division of labor. For a deeper understanding of this process, based on the methodology for studying the emergence of economic systems in the development of market infrastructure, several important stages can be distinguished:

creation of the necessary conditions for the development of the service sector on the basis of private and individual division of labor. At this stage, social and economic factors, as well as technological progress, play an important role. The expansion of the service sector, in turn, leads to the strengthening of the infrastructure.

the emergence and development of infrastructure occurs as a result of the strengthening of interdependencies between various subjects of the market economy. During this process, elements that are missing in the existing system may appear. Such elements serve to increase the efficiency of the infrastructure and further diversify economic activity.

Through these stages, the development of infrastructure becomes important not only from an economic, but also from a social and environmental point of view. Therefore, it is necessary to take an integrated approach to infrastructure development.

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